

ALGAL FLORA OF CENTRAL ASIAN CANALS

Ikramov Nuriddin Boxodirovich

Namangan State University, basic doctoral student of biological sciences.

Namangan (Republic of Uzbekistan) E-mail: www.nuriddin4002@mail.ru.

Annotation. Information about the algal flora of Central Asian canals is insufficient. However, modern research has shown that they have great importance and that the algae have an indicative level of biosecurity and bioecology. That is why the study of the algae of the Central Asian channels has been the main goal. This article deals with algae taxon met in the channels of Central Asia (Big Fergana Canal, South Mirzachul Magistral Canal, Bekabad and Dalvarzin Canals, Turkistan Canal, Kent-Boldiberek Canal, Qizketken Canal, Vakhsh Canal), and comparative analysis with other canals, as well as biological properties. Also, there is information about the coastline sections, the surface of the water surface and the algae found on the surface of underwater stones. The data were studied on the basis of the techniques used by Vasser and other Uzbek scientists and explained in tables.

Key Words: canals, algae, algal flora, diatom, green, yellow-green.

The Big Fergana Canal in the Fergana Valley was built in 1939 to irrigate the waterless areas of Central and Western Fergana. The area of channel passing through the Naryn covers 257,000 hectares of land. 115 types of algae were found on the Big Fergana channel.

In the area where the canal starts dark brown grains consisting of *Phormidium interruptum*, *Ph.incrustatum*, *Ph.corium* are met in the coastal concrete, stones, and mud. Less than 10-15 cm below the water there are grey curtains consisting of *Phormidium papyraceum*, *Ph. Favosum*, *Ph.corium*, and *Lyngby aerugineo-Coerulea* on the surface of the water. In the places where concrete and stones are constantly moistened with water *Stigeoclonium*, *Cladophora fracta*, *Cladophora fracta f.lacustris*, *Stigeoclonium*; diatomic algae *diatomus vulgare*, *Cocconeis placetula* as epiphyte diarrhea in their fibers, and *Symploca muralis*, *Ph.incrustans*, *Phormidium* are met. In the part of the Big Fergana Canal which flows near the city of Kokand, in the concrete coatings, stones, and mud, *Oscillatoria irrigua*, *O.agardhii f.aequicrassa*, *O.rubescens*, *O.Spendida*, *Phormidium corium*, *Ph.favosum*, *Ph.foveocomus*, *Ph.interruptum* which are from blue-greens, *Cladophora glomerata* from greens form the short coatings. Among them *Oscillatoria geminate*, *O.tenuis*, *O.wilei* are blue-green, and Green *Parsisola crispa* from greens are common. In addition to the *phytobenthos*, *phytoplankton* has also developed at the lower Fergana Canal. Tallymen of *Cladophora glomerata* is not developed at the edge of the canal, there is epithelium *Cocconeis placetula*, *C.placentula var. intermedia*, *C.pediculus*, and others.

There are *Oscillatoria geminata*, *O.neglecta*, *O.brevis*, *O.amphybia f.tenuis*, *O.willei*, *Ph.Molle*, *Ph.tenuis*, on the slopes and small stones on the shore, and among them *Merismopedia punctata*, *M.tenuissima*, *Gloeocapsa minuta*, *Gomphosphaeria lacustris*, *Spirulina tenuissima*, *S.major*, *Gloeotrichia natans*, *Pediastrum duplex.genuinum f.convergens*, *Ankistrodesmus densus*, *Scenedesmus bijugatus*, *S.quadricauda*, *Elakatothirix subacuta*, *Binuclearia lauterbornii*, *Cosmaruim granatum*, *Diatoma vulgare*, *Cyclotella comta*, *Synedra ulna*. *Amphirhynchus* are pervasive. None of these taxa grows dominant.

According to the author (Ergashev, 1974), in the blue-green curtains of the wet soils on the shore of all the channels in the Fergana valley *Phormidium subfuscum*, *Ph.corium*, *Ph.cronani*, *Zngbya martensiana* are found, and taxon of *Diatoma*, *Synedra*, *Cocconeis*, *Navicula* are met.

The physical and chemical properties of irrigation canals in the Fergana Valley are not significantly different from that of their rivers where they take water. The regional division of algal floras in these channels is based on types such as *Phormidium incinatum*, *Ph.incrustatum*, *Diatoma vulgare*, *D.heimale* basins which are located in the high mountains and partially mountainous areas of Central Asia; *Phormidium favosum*, *Oscillatorias uplendida*, which are usual for mountainous regions, but also met in central areas; *Merismopedia Tenuissima*, *Gomphosphaeria lacustris*, *Oscillatoria amphibian*, *O.geminata*, *O.tenuis*, *Ph.molle*, *Ankistrodesmus densus*, *Pediastrum duplex*, *Scenedesmus bijugatus* which are usual for lower areas and flatlands.

Studying the algae of the Altyaryk canal, which takes water from the Shakhrikhonsay River in the Fergana valley, is 50 km long and from 5 to 12 m in width (Ergashev, 1974), shows that the variation of a taxon in the end increases. Although, taxon of *Spirogyra* and *Microspora* are widespread among *Cladophora glomerata*, *Enteromorpha intestinalis*; *Oscillatoria tenuis*, *Phormidium corium* from blue greens; *Pediastrum duplex*, *Cosmarium moniliforme*, from greens; *Diatoma elongatum*, *Synedra ulna*, *Cocconeis pediculus*, *Navicula radiosa*, *Gomphonema parvula*, *Cymbella cymbiformis*, from diatoms; and some euglenas (*Euglena acus*, *E.deses*) are also are common.

The Southern Ferghana canal starts from Shakhrikhonsoy and it is 92 km long and water capacity is 50 m³ / sec. The water level is 8-10 m. The dark green dirt on the shoreline is composed of *Phormidium subfuscum*, *Phormidium corium*, *Ph.crouanii*, and *Lyngbya*. *Phormidium favosum*, *Ph.setchellianum*, *Ph.tinctorum* and *Lyngbya aestuarii f.antarctica* and some empty diatomite (*Diatoma*, *Synedra*, *Cocconeis*, *Navicula*, *Nitzschia*) are found along with them.

According to our data, in the North Fergana channel, the length of which is 167 km, 60 types of Blue-greens, 3 types of gold colors, 89 of the Diatoms, 2 of the Denofites, 8 of Eugens and 49 of the Greens; totally 212 types were found.

The Hazarbog Canal (10-12 meters in width, 2-3 meters in depth) in Surkhandarya, takes water from the Tupalang River. *Cladophora glomerata*, *Spirogyra Sp*, *Oedogonium sp.* are very common at the beginning of this channel. Cold-loving alga *Ulothrix zonata*, *Hydrurus foetidus*, along with *Ceratoneis*, *Diatoma hiemale*, *Eucoconeis flexella*, *Synerda goulardii*, *Achnanthes linearis*, *Didymosphenia geminata*, *Cymbella proschkinae*, *Phormidium autumnale*, *Ph.favosum*, and in small amounts *Homoeothrix schizothrichoides*, *Calothrix* is met in this area of the canal. These taxons are not found in the downstream channel.

At the bottom of the channel, the algae have a sharp change in its structure. *Cladophora glamerata* kits are on the shore, some diatoms with *Phormidium tenue*, *Phloronium*, *Ph.papyraseum*, and *Oscillatoria geminate*, *O.sancta*, *Lyngbya aestuaria* on the surface of the moist soil. From 141 algological samples 148 taxon are identified, 29 of them are blue-green, 2 gold-color, 76 diatoms, 4 euglena, 33 green, and 4 taxon algae found in Samarkand, Bukhara, Surkhandarya, and Kashkadarya regions. (Ergashev, 1974).

There are *Cladophora glomerata*, *Microspora pachyderma*, *Spirogyra longata*, among them and on the moist soil surface in thin curtains, *Oscillatoria ammoena*, *O.giminata*,

Phormidium papyraceum, *Cyclotella comta*, *Cyclotella comta*, *Navicula cryptocephala* var. *lanta* *N.cincta*, *Cocconeis placentula*, *Nitzschia apiculata*, *N.microcephala*, *Suriella*, are found in Khirov channel, which is in Mirzachul the length is 135 km long and 20-25 m width, takes water from Syrdarya.

In the middle and bottom of the canal, water flow decreases. There is *Cladophora glomerata*, *Microspora pachyderma* *Spirogyra longata*, in gray curtains *Oscillatoria amoena*, *O.geminata*, *Phormidium papyraceum*. *Navicula cryptocephala* var.*lanta*, *N.cincta*, *Cocconeis placentula*, *Cyclotella comta*, *Nitzschia apiculata*, *N.microcephala*, *Surirella ovate*, *Nitzschia palea*, and others in this area. 214 species and species varieties have been identified from 140 samples taken in Mirzachul irrigation canals, of which 72 are cyanophyta, 45 greens, 11 eugens, 83 diatoms, and 3 taxa.

South Mirzachul main canal takes water from Farhod reservoir, built in Syrdarya, with a length of 92 km, a width of 70m at the beginning, and a depth of 4-5m. Large stones at the beginning of it are intensively dyed with *Cladophora glomerata* *C. Laetelvirens*. *Diatoma vulgare*, *D.vulgare*, *produetum*, *Cocconeis placentula*, *Fragilaria construens*, *Meridion circulare*, *Synedra ulna* are spread among the *Cladophoria* threads. The blue-greens together with diatoms: *Oscillatoria terebriformis*, *O.lemmermannii*, *O.woronichinii*, *O.neglecta*, *O. deeflexoides*, *O.agardii f.sequicrassa*, *Diatoma elongatum*, *Navicula exiqua*, *Cymbella ventricosa*, *Nitzschia closterium* can be found in the bottom part of the phytobenthos of the channel.

The width of the bottom of the Turkestan canal is about 10 m. There is *Phormidium Tenue*, *Oscillatoria amphibia*, *O.angusta*, *Cyclotella comta*, *Syndrera ulna*, *Nitzschia frustulum*, *Navicula radiosa*, *Oscillatoria woronichini*, *O.gemenata cephalo*, *Cymbella amphibia*, *Amphora commutate* in the wetland of the shores. The low quality of the Turkestan canal algae is due to the low level of water purity. There are a total of 88 species and species varieties, 14 of which are belonging to greens, 32 to blue-green, 42 to diatoms, and taxa.

The canals of the Bekabad and Dalvarzin take water from the Farhod reservoir. Most of them are coated with concrete on the shore. Concrete surface covered with curtain consisting of diatoms such as *Diatoma vulgare*, *D.elongatum*, *Fragilaria capucina*, *Navicula cryptocephala* var.*veneta* along with *Scytonema involvens*, *S.velutinum*, *S.tolypothrichoides*, *Oscillatoria laetevirens*. *Scytonema involvens*, *S.velutinum* grows on the surface of the water separator hydrotechnical devices.

A total of 222 species and species of algae species have been identified from the inter-farm, farm irrigation systems (Musaev, 1960), including 52 blue-greens, 1 gold-color, 125 diatoms, 1 Eugena, 39 greens, 3 haras, and 1 red alga.

The Turkestan trunk canal receives water from the Farhod reservoir. Total length is 140 km; water consumption is 45 m³ / s. At the beginning of the channel width is 30 m, the bottom width is 24-25 m, the water depth is 1.5-2 m, and its initial 50-60 meters is concretized. The surface is covered with *Cladophora glomerata* and *Spirogyra* sp. There are *Diatoma vulgare*, *Cocconeis placentula*, *Lyngby kassinaju*, *Phormidium corium*, *Ph.interrupta*, *Ph.molle f.tenue*, *Oscillatoria amoena*, *O.splendida*, *Navicula cryptocephala*, *Schizotrice latea*, *Stigoclonium flagelliferum*, *Scenedesmus bijugatus*, *Cosmarium formosulum*, *Gomphonema olivaceum* among the fibers of the cladophora.

The effect of taxon on the watercourse on the formation of the algae at the beginning of the channel is great.

The algal flora of the middle part of the Turkestan canal is not as rich as at the beginning. *Cladophora glomerata* is less spread. Most of the taxon found at the beginning are not found here. There are *Oscillatoria amphibia*, *O. Jasorvensis*, *Phormidium corium*, *Ph.tenue*, *Navicula cincta*, *Cymbella affinis*, *Surirella* in the middle of the canal. *Ulothrix zonata*, *U. Tenerrima* and *Sphaeronosta coeruleum*, *S.pruniforme* and *Stranostoc linkia* were found in the right and left banks of the river Sayra (Kazakhstan, Chimkent region).

At the beginning of the Kent-Boldiberek canal, *Hydrurus foetidus* from gold-colors, *Ulothrix* from green, and *Stigeoclonium mamillosum*, *Schizohriks lutea*, *Leptobasis caucasica* are common in his area.

Vaucheria geminate in *Alamanda*, *V. Dichotoma* among their palms and on the moist soil *Oscillatoria terebriformis* *F.caucasica* and others were found in Hidirarik canal which takes water from Aksu River.

It was identified that spherical talloms of *Stratonostoc linkia* on the stones on coastline and *Cladophora fracta* and *C.flexuosa* are common in fast-flowing parts of Oytol canal (near the city of Merki, Jambul Province, Kazakhstan)

Because of the water muddiness in the Qizketken Canal, which takes its waters from Amu Darya River, the algae are not so rich. *Osillatoria rupicola*, *O.limosa*, *Lyngbya aesthearti*, *Spirulina major*, *S.tenuissima*, *cymbella lanceolata*, *Gyrosigma scalproides*, *Nitzschia tenuirustris*, *N.obtusa*.*scalpelliformis* from greens are common there.

From the irrigation canals of the Amu Darya River, 170 taxa of algae, 53 of them are blue-greens, 80 diatoms, 1 yellow-green, 5 euglenas, 82 greens, and 1 hara taxon were found (Ergashev, Rsimbetov 1970, Rsimbetov, 1973).

The Vaxsh canal takes water from the reservoir with the same name. Its length is 366 km, its width is 40-45 m, and the water depth is up to 6 meters. There are *Stigeoclonium lubricum*, *S.subuligerum*, *S.flagelliferum*, *Microskopora tumidula*, *Oscillatoria amoena*, *O.willei*, *Ph.crouanii*, *Ph.papyraceum* on the moistened surface of the soils at the beginning and *Oscillatoria amphigranulata*, *O.agardii f.wislouchii*, *O.amoena*, *O.neglecta*, *O.terebriformis*, *O.tenuis*, *Spirulina Major*, *Phormidium corium* at the central and bottom parts of the canal. 44 taxon, 11 greens, 15 diatoms, and 18 blue-green algae were found on the Vakhsh main canal.

The Great Chuy Canal (Kyrgyzstan) is 160 km long and 57 km crosses Kazakhstan's Jambul region. Its width is 40-44 m in the Chuy district, 32-34 m. The surfaces of the stones are covered with chained green tallom of *Cladophora glomerata*, and it is also covered with *Diatoma vulgare var.productum*, *D.elongatum*, *Cocconeis placentula* var.intermedia. Among the cladophoria threads, *Ulotrix Tenerimma*, *U.zonata* and *Binuclearia lauterbornii* are found in one or two threads.

In the middle of the Chuy canal, its width slightly decreases (34-35m) and the water surface is 31-32m. *Cladofora glomerata* is common in the wet soils of the canal. *Diatoma* is almost entirely epithelial in elongated cells. *Synedra ulna* and *Melosira varians* are found among cladofora threads. *Cocconeis plaentula*, *Cymbella*, *Surirella Ovata*, *Gyrosigma quetzine*, *Ultrihs Tenerrima*, *U.aequalis*, *Oedogonium sp.*, *Cymbella affinis*, *C.ventricosa*, *Oscillatoria geminate*, *Cosmarium reniforme*, and basically in plankton, *Binuclearia lanterbornii* are spread in benthos at this area.

There are 77 species and forms of alga, 2 of which are Eugens, 17 greens, 24 blue-greens, and 34 diatoms taxon, found in the Big Chuy canal. The phytobenthos of this canal is not much different from the other canals in Central Asia.

In the algae of the algae in Uzbekistan and Central Asia, we find the largest number of the taxon in the irrigation canals (222 taxa) in Tashkent and in the channels of Mirzachul (214 taxa). The number of these taxa is more than 106 in comparison with 11 and 98 respectively. The total number of species found in the Fergana valley was 63, to channels in downstream of the Amu Darya River 54, in the south of the country 32. The average number is less than 6 digits.

Summary.

According to the literature, the aluminum structure of the trunk and other channels in Ferghana valley, particularly in the Ferghana valley, is still the basis of the samples collected during expeditions. The algal flora, which develops on one of the major highways, has not been surveyed on a clear objective, task. A comparison of the number of the taxon in Algal flora shows that the percentage of blue-green algae in the main canals in the Ferghana Valley was high than 40 years ago, indicating that the level of water pollution in the main canals is now increasing.

When we compared the number of the taxon in separate aliphatic units, which form the Algal flora, these were identified: The highest point of an average number of eleven figures we have compared was in diatom alga (48 taxa); on average 41.35%. The percentage of diatomite alga at the Tashkent irrigation canals is more from median degree by 14.93%, in the southern canals of the republic - by 14.93%, in the Turkestan canal (47.73%) by 6.35%, in the Big Chuy canal (44.16%) more than 2.78%. The percentage of diatoms found in algae in the Fergana valley has averaged as high as the percentage of algae (41.34%).

Blue-green algae are in the next place with 32.0% (average 37 taxa). The total altitude of green algae in the Big Fergana canal (52.38%) was up by 20.38%, in the Northern Fergana canal (51.67%) - by 19.67%, in the Vakhsh Canal Aluminum (40.91%) - by 8.91%, in the total canal in the Ferghana Valley (37.43%) 5.43%, Turkestan canal algal flora - 4.36%, with a large number of blue-green algae. In other cases, the percentage of blue-green algae is less than average.

11 of the green algae compared to the total number of taxa was 21.55%. There was no big difference in this indicator compared to others. The high percentages (40.74%) in the Southern Fergana canal have been clearly above average - 19.95%, followed by the Northern Fergana channel - 6.78%.

Differences in greenhouse taxon percentages in the south of the Republic (22.23%), Vakhsh (25.0%), Big Chuy (22.08%) and Mirzachol (21.03%) canals have not been great. The lowest similarity was 5.64% lower than the average for the Turkestan canal Algae (15.91%).

Literature used.

1. Alimjanova Kh.A. Patterns of distribution of algae in the Chirchik river basin and their importance in determining water bodies' ecological and sanitary state. Tashkent. "Fan". 2007
2. Zerov D.K. Essay on the phylogeny of avascular plants, "Naukava Dumka", Kiev. 1972.
3. Ergashev A.E. Formation of the algal flora of artificial reservoirs of Central Asia. VKN: Sporea plants of Central Asia. "Fan" T. 1969.

4. Buriev S.B. Microalgae as wastewater purifiers and facilities for the development of effective water conservation biotechnology: author. dis ... dr. biol. science .. Tashkent. 1993 - 43 sec.
5. Alimjanova Kh.A., Shaiimkulova MA Algoflora of the Akbuura River and its importance in assessing water quality. - Tashkent. 2008. 125 p.
6. Vinogradova KL, Gollerbakh MM, Zauer LM, Sdobnikova N.V. Key to freshwater algae of the USSR. Issue 13. Green algae. Chlorophyta: Siphonclad Classes, Siphon Classes. Siphocladophyceae, Siphonophyceae. Edge algae - Rhodophyta. Brown algae - Phaeophyta. L.: Science. Leningrad branch. 1980. -248 p.
7. Ann Tu Van, Veronika Sommer, Karin Glaser. The Ecophysiological Performance and Traits of Genera within the Stichococcus-like Clade (Trebouxiophyceae) under Matric and Osmotic Stress. *Microorganisms* 2021, 9(9), 1816.
8. Brown, L.M.; Hellebust, J.A. Sorbitol and Proline as Intracellular Osmotic Solutes in the Green Alga *Stichococcus bacillaris*. *Can. J. Bot.* 1978, 56, 676–679.
9. Ladislav Hodac, Christine Hallmann, Karolin Spitzer, Josef Elster, Fabian Faßhauer, Nicole Brinkmann, Daniela Lepka, Vaibhav Diwan, Thomas Friedl. Widespread green algae *Chlorella* and *Stichococcus* exhibit polar-temperate and tropical-temperate biogeography. *FEMS Microbiology. Ecology.* 92, 2016. fiw 122.
10. Lewin, R.A. A Marine *Stichococcus* sp. Which Requires Vitamin B12 (Cobalamin). *J. Gen. Microbiol.* 1954, 4, 93–96.
11. Sommer, V.; Mikhailyuk, T.; Glaser, K.; Karsten, U. Uncovering Unique Green Algae and Cyanobacteria Isolated from Biocrusts in Highly Saline Potash Tailing Pile Habitats, Using an Integrative Approach. *Microorganisms* 2020, 8, 1667
12. Thomas Pröschold & Tatyana Darienko. The green puzzle *Stichococcus* (Trebouxiophyceae, Chlorophyta): New generic and species concept among this widely distributed genus. // *Phytotaxa*, 2020. No.2:4. 31 P.